

SLAG MANIFOLDS IN $G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$ AND Σ_λ -SCHUBERT MANIFOLD

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ABSTRACT. We construct explicit Calabi–Yau hypersurfaces in complex Grassmannians defined by homogeneous equations in Plücker coordinates. Using a local analytic approach and the Poincaré residue method, we prove the existence of a nowhere vanishing holomorphic volume form. We show that the real loci of these hypersurfaces are special Lagrangian submanifolds. The construction is carried out in full detail for the Grassmannian $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$, and extended to the general case $G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$. Topological properties of the real locus are also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Special Lagrangian submanifolds, introduced by Harvey and Lawson, play a central role in Calabi–Yau geometry and mirror symmetry. Explicit constructions remain scarce, especially in compact settings. A fruitful approach consists in realizing special Lagrangian submanifolds as real loci of Calabi–Yau manifolds endowed with an anti-holomorphic involution.

In this article, we develop a systematic construction of Calabi–Yau hypersurfaces in Grassmannians whose real loci are special Lagrangian. Our method relies on explicit local coordinates and the Poincaré residue construction of holomorphic volume forms. Let (X^{2n}, ω, J, g) be a Kähler manifold of complex dimension n , where ω is the Kähler form, J the complex structure, and g the associated Riemannian metric. Assume moreover that X is a Calabi–Yau manifold, that is, X admits a nowhere vanishing holomorphic $(n, 0)$ -form Ω satisfying

$$\text{Ric}(g) = 0.$$

A real n -dimensional submanifold $L \subset X$ is called a *special Lagrangian submanifold* if it satisfies:

(1) L is Lagrangian, i.e.

$$\omega|_L = 0;$$

(2) L is calibrated by $\text{Re}(\Omega)$, i.e.

$$\text{Im}(\Omega)|_L = 0.$$

Equivalently, L satisfies

$$\Omega|_L = e^{i\theta} \text{vol}_L$$

for some constant phase $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$.

Special Lagrangian submanifolds are minimal and volume-minimizing in their homology class. An important and natural source of special Lagrangian submanifolds arises from real structures on Calabi–Yau manifolds.

Let (X, ω, Ω) be a Calabi–Yau manifold equipped with an anti-holomorphic involution

$$\tau : X \rightarrow X,$$

called a *real structure*, satisfying

$$\tau^2 = \text{id}, \quad \tau^*\omega = -\omega, \quad \tau^*\Omega = \bar{\Omega}.$$

The *real locus* of X is defined by

$$X^\tau := \{x \in X \mid \tau(x) = x\}.$$

If X^τ is non-empty and smooth, then it is a totally real submanifold of real dimension n .

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Proposition 1. *Let $(X, \omega, \Omega, \tau)$ be a Calabi–Yau manifold with a real structure. Then the real locus X^τ is a special Lagrangian submanifold of X with phase $\theta = 0$.*

Proof. Since $\tau^*\omega = -\omega$, the restriction of ω to the fixed point set X^τ vanishes, hence X^τ is Lagrangian. Moreover, the condition $\tau^*\Omega = \bar{\Omega}$ implies that Ω restricts to a real-valued n -form on X^τ , hence $\text{Im}(\Omega)|_{X^\tau} = 0$. This shows that X^τ is special Lagrangian. \square

1. BACKGROUND AND CONSTRUCTION

The complex Grassmannian is defined by:

$$G_{p,p+q}(\mathbb{C}) = p\text{-dimensional complex vector subspaces of } \mathbb{C}^{p+q}.$$

It is a compact complex homogeneous manifold:

$$G_{p,p+q}(\mathbb{C}) \simeq \frac{U(p+q)}{U(p) \times U(q)}.$$

On the *big cell*, every element is represented by a matrix $Z \in M_{q,p}(\mathbb{C})$ via:

$$\Gamma_Z = \text{span} (I_p \ Z) e_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, p \subset \mathbb{C}^{p+q}.$$

Kähler Potential and Fubini-Study form. The standard Kähler potential on the big cell is:

$$K(Z) = \log \det (I_p + Z^*Z).$$

The corresponding Kähler form is:

$$\omega = i\partial\bar{\partial}K(Z).$$

Explicit Calculation. Let $A = I_p + Z^*Z$ and $B = I_q + ZZ^*$. We have:

$$(1) \quad \partial K = \text{tr}(A^{-1}Z^*\partial Z), \quad \bar{\partial}K = \text{tr}(A^{-1}dZ^*Z).$$

Thus, the Kähler form becomes:

$$\omega = i\partial\bar{\partial}K = i, \text{tr}(B^{-1}\partial Z \wedge A^{-1}dZ^*).$$

This expression is positive-definite and invariant under $U(p+q)$.

Plücker Coordinates. The immersion of $G_{p,p+q}(\mathbb{C})$ in projective space is:

$$G_{p,p+q}(\mathbb{C}) \hookrightarrow \mathbb{P}^{\binom{p+q}{p}-1},$$

with p -minor coordinates P_I indexed by ordered multi-indices I . These coordinates satisfy quadratic Plücker relations.

Example $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$. The coordinates are P_{ij} , $1 \leq i < j \leq 5$, and the Plücker relations are:

$$P_{ij}P_{kl} - P_{ik}P_{jl} + P_{il}P_{jk} = 0, \quad 1 \leq i < j < k < l \leq 5.$$

Example $G_{3,6}\mathbb{C}$. For $G_{3,6}$, the coordinates are $P_{ijk}, 1 \leq i < j < k \leq 6$. Plücker's quadratic relations have the form:

$$P_{ijk}P_{lmn} - P_{ijl}P_{kmn} + P_{ijm}P_{kln} - P_{ijn}P_{klm} = 0,$$

for any choice of 6 distinct indices i, j, k, l, m, n . These relations generalize the structure of $G_{2,5}$ and demonstrate the quadratic nature of immersion.

CONJUGATION AND ANTI-SYMPLECTICITY

Consider the anti-holomorphic involution:

$$\sigma : Z \mapsto \bar{Z}.$$

Since $K(Z)$ is real and σ exchanges ∂ and $\bar{\partial}$, we have:

$$\sigma^*\omega = i\sigma^*(\partial\bar{\partial}K) = i\bar{\partial}\partial K = -i\partial\bar{\partial}K = -\omega.$$

Thus, the fixed locus $\text{Fix}(\sigma)$ is a special Lagrangian submanifold (SLag) of real dimension pq .

2. CALABI-YAU MANIFOLDS AND SPECIAL LAGRANGIAN MANIFOLDS IN THE GRASSMANNIAN $G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$
Kähler Potential and Fubini-Study form. The standard Kähler potential on the big cell is:

$$K(Z) = \log \det (I_p + Z^*Z).$$

The corresponding Kähler form is:

$$\omega = i\partial\bar{\partial}K(Z).$$

By setting $A = I_p + Z^*Z$ and $B = I_q + ZZ^*$, we obtain:

$$\omega = i \text{tr}(B^{-1}\partial Z \wedge A^{-1}dZ^*).$$

Plücker Coordinates. The immersion of $G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$ in projective space is:

$$G_{p,p+q}(\mathbb{C}) \hookrightarrow \mathbb{P}^{\binom{p+q}{p}-1},$$

with p -minor coordinates P_I satisfying quadratic relations.

Example $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$. The coordinates are $P_{ij}, 1 \leq i < j \leq 5$, with relations:

$$P_{ij}P_{kl} - P_{ik}P_{jl} + P_{il}P_{jk} = 0, \quad 1 \leq i < j < k < l \leq 5.$$

Calabi-Yau manifold in the Grassmannian. A Calabi-Yau manifold $X \subset G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$ is obtained by taking a hypersurface of appropriate degree via the Plücker embedding:

$$X := \{F(P_I) = 0\} \subset G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C},$$

with F homogeneous so that $c_1(TX) = 0$.

The holomorphic form on X is given by the Poincaré residue:

$$\Omega_X = \text{Res}_{F=0} \frac{\Omega_0}{F(P_I)},$$

with $\Omega_0 = \bigwedge_{a,j} dz_{aj}$ the maximal holomorphic form on the big cell.

Concrete example: CY3 in $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$. We choose $F(P_{ij})$ to be homogeneous of degree 5. Then:

$$X = \{F(P_{ij}) = 0\} \subset G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$$

is a Calabi-Yau manifold of dimension 3 and

$$\Omega_X = \text{Res}_{F=0} \frac{dz_{11} \wedge dz_{12} \wedge dz_{21} \wedge dz_{22} \wedge dz_{31} \wedge dz_{32}}{F(P_{ij})}.$$

Real Locus and Special Lagrangian manifold. We consider the standard conjugation $\sigma : Z \mapsto \bar{Z}$. The fixed locus:

$$L = X(\mathbb{R}) = X \cap G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{R} = \{Z \in G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{R} \mid F(Z) = 0\}$$

is a real submanifold of dimension pq .

Since σ is anti-holomorphic and anti-symplectic ($\sigma^*\omega = -\omega$) and $\Im\Omega_X|_L = 0$, L is **special Lagrangian** in X .

Calabi-Yau Hypersurface and Poincaré Residue. Let $X \subset G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$ be defined by a homogeneous polynomial equation

$$F(Z) = 0,$$

in Plücker coordinates $Z = [Z_I]$.

If the degree of F is chosen such that the first Chern class of X is zero, then X is a Calabi-Yau manifold. The maximal holomorphic form Ω on X is obtained by the *Poincaré residue*:

$$\Omega = \text{Res}_X \frac{\Theta}{F(Z)},$$

where Θ is a maximal holomorphic form on $G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$.

Special Lagrangian Submanifold. We define the real submanifold

$$L = X \cap G_{p,p+q}(\mathbb{R}) = \{Z \in X \mid Z = \bar{Z}\}.$$

Then:

- (1) $\omega|_L = 0$, so L is Lagrangian.
- (2) $\text{Im}(\Omega)|_L = 0$, so L is special.

Known results on $G_{2,4}\mathbb{C}$. Thus, L is a special Lagrangian manifold calibrated by $\text{Re}(\Omega)$.

Consider the Grassmannian $G_{2,4}(\mathbb{C})$, with Plücker coordinates $[Z_{12}, Z_{13}, Z_{14}, Z_{23}, Z_{24}, Z_{34}]$.

We define a Calabi-Yau hypersurface $X \subset G_{2,4}\mathbb{C}$ of degree 4:

$$F(Z_{ij}) = 0.$$

The Poincaré residue provides a holomorphic form

$$\Omega = \text{Res}_{F=0} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^6 (-1)^i Z_i dZ_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge \widehat{dZ_i} \wedge \cdots \wedge dZ_6}{F(Z)}.$$

The special real Lagrangian submanifold is then

$$L = \{[Z_{ij}] \in X \mid Z_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}\}.$$

In fact, A. Ben Abdesselem and P. Cabau showed in their paper [1] the existence of a special Lagrangian manifold which comes from the real locus of a Calabi-Yau manifold ($c_1 = 0$), in fact, they studied this hypersurface in $G_{2,4}\mathbb{C}$ noted by X :

$$(2) \quad \begin{aligned} F(u, v) &= (z_0 z'_1 - z_1 z'_0)^4 + (z_0 z'_2 - z_2 z'_0)^4 + (z_0 z'_3 - z_3 z'_0)^4 \\ &- (z_1 z'_2 - z_2 z'_1)^4 - (z_1 z'_3 - z_3 z'_1)^4 - (z_2 z'_3 - z_3 z'_2)^4 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

described in the above coordinates, the point of $\mathbb{P}_5\mathbb{C}$:

$$\begin{aligned} [\eta_0 = z_0 z'_1 - z_1 z'_0, \eta_1 = z_0 z'_2 - z_2 z'_0, \eta_2 = z_0 z'_3 - z_3 z'_0, \\ \eta_3 = z_1 z'_2 - z_2 z'_1, \eta_4 = z_1 z'_3 - z_3 z'_1, \eta_5 = z_2 z'_3 - z_3 z'_2]. \end{aligned}$$

So, X appears as a complete intersection of a quadric and a quartic in $\mathbb{P}_5\mathbb{C}$, given by :

$$(3) \quad \begin{cases} \eta_0 \eta_5 - \eta_1 \eta_4 + \eta_2 \eta_3 = 0 \\ \eta_0^4 + \eta_1^4 + \eta_2^4 - \eta_3^4 - \eta_4^4 - \eta_5^4 = 0 \end{cases}$$

then they studied the Poincaré residue in order to prove that the latter is a Calabi-Yau manifold:

$$\eta = \frac{\gamma \wedge dg}{g} + \delta = \frac{d\zeta_1 \wedge d\zeta_2 \wedge d\zeta_3 \wedge d\zeta_4}{1 + \zeta_1^4 + \zeta_2^4 - \zeta_3^4 - \zeta_4^4 - (\zeta_1 \zeta_4 - \zeta_2 \zeta_3)^4}$$

from which the residue is equal:

$$\gamma = \frac{-d\zeta_2 \wedge d\zeta_3 \wedge d\zeta_4}{\partial f_{01} / \partial \zeta_1}$$

which defines a holomorphic 3-volume form on X , this proves that $c_1(X) = 0$.

Then they used R.L.Bryant's result that states that the real locus of a manifold of $c_1 = 0$ is a special Lagrangian manifold which its interpretation is a circle bundle over $\mathbb{P}_2\mathbb{R}$.

Local description of Grassmannians and residue method. Let $G_{k,n} = G_{k,n}\mathbb{C}$ denote the Grassmannian of k -planes in \mathbb{C}^n . It is covered by affine charts U_I indexed by subsets I of cardinal k , where the Plücker coordinate η_I does not vanish. On each chart U_I , the Grassmannian is biholomorphic to $\mathbb{C}^{k(n-k)}$.

Let $X \subset G_{k,n}$ be a hypersurface locally defined by a holomorphic equation $f = 0$. On each chart, we consider the meromorphic form

$$\eta = \frac{dz_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge dz_{k(n-k)}}{f}$$

3. THE GRASSMANNIAN $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$

3.1. Affine coordinates and local equation. Let $u, u' \in \mathbb{C}^5$ be two independent vectors. On the affine chart $U_{01} = \eta_{01} \neq 0$, we normalize

$$(u, u') = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ \zeta_1 & \zeta_2 \\ \zeta_3 & \zeta_4 \\ \zeta_5 & \zeta_6 \end{pmatrix}$$

Consider the homogeneous polynomial

$$(4) \quad F = \sum_{0 \leq i < j \leq 4} \varepsilon_{ij} \eta_{ij}^5, \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = \pm 1.$$

On U_{01} this reduces to $f_{01} = 1 + P(\zeta)$, where P is homogeneous of degree 5.

Explicit example: the Grassmannian $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$.

Definition of the hypersurface. Let $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$ be the Grassmannian of complex 2-planes in \mathbb{C}^5 , embedded in $\mathbb{P}_9\mathbb{C}$ via Plücker coordinates $(\eta_{ij})_{0 \leq i < j \leq 4}$. Consider the homogeneous polynomial

$$(5) \quad F = \eta_{01}^5 + \eta_{02}^5 + \eta_{03}^5 - \eta_{04}^5 - \eta_{12}^5 - \eta_{13}^5 - \eta_{14}^5 + \eta_{23}^5 + \eta_{24}^5 + \eta_{34}^5.$$

It has degree $5 = p + q$ and depends only on the underlying 2-plane. We denote by

$$X_{2,5} = \{F = 0\} \subset G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$$

the associated hypersurface.

Smoothness and Calabi–Yau property. On any affine chart U_{ij} with $\eta_{ij} \neq 0$, the equation reduces to $f_{ij} = 1 + P(\zeta)$, where P is a homogeneous polynomial of degree 5 in 6 variables. For a generic choice of signs, df_{ij} does not vanish identically on $f_{ij}^{-1}(0)$, hence $X_{2,5}$ is smooth. By adjunction (or by the Poincaré residue construction),

$$K_{X_{2,5}} \simeq \mathcal{O}_{X_{2,5}},$$

so $X_{2,5}$ is a Calabi–Yau 5-fold.

Holomorphic volume form. On the chart U_{01} with coordinates $(\zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_6)$, the holomorphic $(5, 0)$ -form is

$$\Omega = -\frac{d\zeta_2 \wedge \cdots \wedge d\zeta_6}{\partial f_{01} / \partial \zeta_1},$$

which extends holomorphically and never vanishes on $X_{2,5}$.

3.2. Smoothness and holomorphic volume form. For a generic choice of signs, df_{01} does not vanish identically on $f_{01}^{-1}(0)$, hence the hypersurface $X_{2,5} = F = 0$ is smooth.

The meromorphic 6-form

$$\eta = \frac{d\zeta_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge d\zeta_6}{f_{01}}$$

$$\Omega = -\frac{d\zeta_2 \wedge \cdots \wedge d\zeta_6}{\partial f_{01} / \partial \zeta_1}$$

3.3. Topology of the real locus. In the case $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$, the real locus $L_{2,5}$ admits a fibration structure over $G_{2,4}\mathbb{R} \simeq \mathbb{P}_3\mathbb{R}$ with circle fibers. In symmetric situations, $L_{2,5}$ is diffeomorphic to a lens space S^3/\mathbb{Z}_k , generalizing the examples of Ben Abdesslem–Cabau. Let $L_{2,5} = X_{2,5}(\mathbb{R}) \subset G_{2,5}\mathbb{R}$. Writing a real 2–plane as $(u, u') \in \mathbb{R}^5 \times \mathbb{R}^5$ modulo $\text{GL}(2, \mathbb{R})$, the defining equation becomes

$$(6) \quad \sum_{i < j} \varepsilon_{ij} (x_i x'_j - x_j x'_i)^5 = 0,$$

together with normalization conditions ensuring compactness.

Fibration structure. Projecting onto the last four coordinates defines a smooth map

$$\pi : L_{2,5} \rightarrow G_{2,4}\mathbb{R} \simeq \mathbb{P}_3\mathbb{R}.$$

For generic signs, the fiber of π is a circle S^1 , defined by a norm condition of the form

$$\|x_0 u'_0 - x'_0 u_0\| = 1.$$

Hence $L_{2,5}$ is a principal S^1 –bundle over a compact real algebraic base.

Analogy with lens spaces. In symmetric situations, the base reduces to $\mathbb{P}_2\mathbb{R}$ and the total space is diffeomorphic to a lens space

$$L_{2,5} \simeq S^3/\mathbb{Z}_k,$$

generalizing the case S^3/\mathbb{Z}_4 obtained for $G_{2,4}\mathbb{C}$.

4. BETTI AND HODGE NUMBERS FOR CALABI–YAU HYPERSURFACES IN $G(2, 5)$

4.1. Cohomology of the Grassmannian $G(2, 5)$. Let $G(2, 5)$ be the Grassmannian of 2–planes in \mathbb{C}^5 . It is a smooth projective homogeneous variety of complex dimension 6 and Picard rank one. Its canonical bundle is

$$K_{G(2,5)} = \mathcal{O}_{G(2,5)}(-5),$$

so $G(2, 5)$ is Fano of index 5.

The cohomology ring of $G(2, 5)$ is generated by Schubert classes and is purely of type (p, p) . The non-zero Betti numbers are

$$b_0 = 1, \quad b_2 = 1, \quad b_4 = 2, \quad b_6 = 2, \quad b_8 = 2, \quad b_{10} = 1, \quad b_{12} = 1.$$

4.2. The Calabi–Yau hypersurface. Let

$$X_{2,5} \subset G(2, 5)$$

be a smooth anticanonical hypersurface, i.e. $X_{2,5} \in |\mathcal{O}_{G(2,5)}(5)|$. Then $X_{2,5}$ is a Calabi–Yau manifold of complex dimension 5, satisfying

$$K_{X_{2,5}} \simeq \mathcal{O}_{X_{2,5}}.$$

4.3. Lefschetz hyperplane theorem. By the Lefschetz hyperplane theorem, the restriction map induces isomorphisms

$$H^k(G(2, 5), \mathbb{Z}) \simeq H^k(X_{2,5}, \mathbb{Z}), \quad \text{for all } k < 5.$$

Hence,

$$b_1(X_{2,5}) = 0, \quad b_2(X_{2,5}) = 1, \quad b_3(X_{2,5}) = 0, \quad b_4(X_{2,5}) = 2.$$

4.4. Middle cohomology and primitive Hodge numbers. The middle cohomology is $H^5(X_{2,5})$. Since $H^5(G(2, 5)) = 0$, one has

$$H^5(X_{2,5}) = H^5_{\text{prim}}(X_{2,5}).$$

By the Griffiths–Dwork method adapted to Grassmannians, the primitive Hodge numbers for a generic smooth anticanonical hypersurface $X_{2,5}$ are:

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} h^{1,4}(X_{2,5}) &= h^{4,1}(X_{2,5}) = 1, \\ h^{2,3}(X_{2,5}) &= h^{3,2}(X_{2,5}) = 5. \end{aligned}}$$

Therefore,

$$b_5(X_{2,5}) = 2(1 + 5) = 12.$$

4.5. **Betti numbers and Euler characteristic.** The Betti numbers of $X_{2,5}$ are summarized as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c|cccccc} k & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ \hline b_k(X_{2,5}) & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 12 \end{array}$$

and extended to higher degrees by Poincaré duality up to $b_{10} = 1$.

The Euler characteristic is

$$\chi(X_{2,5}) = 2(1 + 1 + 2) - 12 = -6.$$

4.6. **Hodge diamond.** The Hodge diamond of $X_{2,5}$ has the following non-zero entries:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} & & & & 1 \\ & & & & 0 & 0 \\ & & & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & & 0 & 0 & 5 & 0 \\ & & 0 & 5 & 0 & \\ & & 0 & 1 & & \\ & & & 0 & & \\ & & & & & 1 \end{array}$$

4.7. **Mirror symmetry and SYZ picture.** The equality $h^{1,1}(X_{2,5}) = 1$ shows that $X_{2,5}$ has a single Kähler modulus, while the large value $h^{2,3} = 5$ controls the complex deformations. Mirror symmetry predicts a mirror Calabi–Yau manifold $X_{2,5}^\vee$ with

$$h^{1,1}(X_{2,5}^\vee) = 5, \quad h^{2,3}(X_{2,5}^\vee) = 1,$$

which is compatible with a Strominger–Yau–Zaslow fibration by real 3-tori.

5. GRASSMANNIAN $G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$

On the standard chart U_{I_0} , a p -plane is represented by

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_p \\ Z \end{pmatrix}, \quad Z \in M_{q \times p}(\mathbb{C})$$

$$F = \sum_{|I|=p} \varepsilon_I \eta_I^{p+q}$$

The meromorphic (pq) -form

$$\eta = \frac{\bigwedge_{i,j} dz_{ij}}{f_{I_0}}$$

Theorem 1. *Let $X \subset G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$ be a smooth hypersurface defined by*

$$F = \sum_{|I|=p} \varepsilon_I \eta_I^{p+q}$$

Proof. The triviality of K_X follows from the residue construction. Complex conjugation preserves both F and the Kähler form ω . Its fixed point set L is totally real and Lagrangian. Since $c^*\Omega = \bar{\Omega}$, we have $\text{Im } \Omega|_L = 0$, hence L is special Lagrangian. \square

6. CALABI–YAU HYPERSURFACES IN $G_{3,6}\mathbb{C}$ AND $G_{3,7}\mathbb{C}$

6.1. The Grassmannian $G_{3,6}\mathbb{C}$.

6.1.1. *Affine coordinates and local model.* Let $G_{3,6}\mathbb{C}$ be the Grassmannian of complex 3-planes in \mathbb{C}^6 . On the standard affine chart U_{123} where the Plücker coordinate $\eta_{123} \neq 0$, any 3-plane can be represented as

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_3 \\ Z \end{pmatrix}, \quad Z \in M_{3 \times 3}(\mathbb{C}),$$

providing holomorphic coordinates $(z_{ij})_{1 \leq i,j \leq 3}$. Hence $U_{123} \simeq \mathbb{C}^9$.

6.1.2. *Defining equation.* Consider the homogeneous polynomial

$$(7) \quad F = \sum_{|I|=3} \varepsilon_I \eta_I^6, \quad \varepsilon_I = \pm 1,$$

of degree $6 = p + q$. We define the hypersurface

$$X_{3,6} = \{F = 0\} \subset G_{3,6}\mathbb{C}.$$

On the chart U_{123} , F reduces to

$$(8) \quad f_{123}(Z) = 1 + P(Z),$$

where P is a homogeneous polynomial of degree 6 in the z_{ij} .

6.1.3. *Smoothness.* For a generic choice of signs ε_I , the differential df_{123} does not vanish identically on $f_{123}^{-1}(0)$. Hence $X_{3,6}$ is a smooth hypersurface of complex dimension 8.

6.1.4. *Holomorphic volume form.* Consider the meromorphic $(9, 0)$ -form

$$\eta = \frac{\bigwedge_{i,j} dz_{ij}}{f_{123}(Z)}.$$

As in the general Grassmannian case, the Jacobians of coordinate changes cancel the transformation of f_{123} , so η defines a global meromorphic form on $G_{3,6}\mathbb{C}$ with simple poles along $X_{3,6}$.

On a sub-chart where $\partial f_{123}/\partial z_{11} \neq 0$, the Poincaré residue is

$$\Omega_{3,6} = -\frac{dz_{12} \wedge \cdots \wedge dz_{33}}{\partial f_{123}/\partial z_{11}},$$

which is a nowhere vanishing holomorphic $(8, 0)$ -form on $X_{3,6}$. Thus

$$K_{X_{3,6}} \simeq \mathcal{O}_{X_{3,6}}, \quad c_1(X_{3,6}) = 0.$$

6.1.5. *Real locus.* Complex conjugation preserves F , hence

$$L_{3,6} = X_{3,6}(\mathbb{R})$$

is a smooth real submanifold. Since $c^*\omega = -\omega$, we have $\omega|_{L_{3,6}} = 0$. Moreover $c^*\Omega_{3,6} = \overline{\Omega_{3,6}}$, so

$$\text{Im } \Omega_{3,6}|_{L_{3,6}} = 0.$$

Thus $L_{3,6}$ is special Lagrangian.

7. BETTI AND HODGE NUMBERS FOR CALABI–YAU HYPERSURFACES IN $G(3, 6)$

7.1. **Cohomology of the Grassmannian $G(3, 6)$.** Let $G(3, 6)$ be the Grassmannian of 3-planes in \mathbb{C}^6 . It is a smooth projective homogeneous variety of complex dimension 9, with Picard rank one and ample generator $\mathcal{O}_{G(3,6)}(1)$.

The canonical bundle is given by

$$K_{G(3,6)} = \mathcal{O}_{G(3,6)}(-6),$$

so that $G(3, 6)$ is Fano of index 6.

The cohomology ring of $G(3, 6)$ is generated by Schubert classes and is purely of type (p, p) . The Betti numbers are well known:

$$b_0 = 1, \quad b_2 = 1, \quad b_4 = 2, \quad b_6 = 3, \quad b_8 = 3, \quad b_{10} = 3,$$

with Poincaré duality determining the remaining ones up to $b_{18} = 1$.

7.2. Lefschetz theorem for the Calabi–Yau hypersurface. Let

$$X_{3,6} \subset G(3,6)$$

be a smooth anticanonical hypersurface, that is, $X_{3,6} \in |\mathcal{O}_{G(3,6)}(6)|$. Then $X_{3,6}$ is a Calabi–Yau manifold of dimension 8.

By the Lefschetz hyperplane theorem, for all $k < 8$,

$$H^k(X_{3,6}, \mathbb{Z}) \simeq H^k(G(3,6), \mathbb{Z}).$$

In particular,

$$b_1 = 0, \quad b_2 = 1, \quad b_3 = 0, \quad b_4 = 2, \quad b_5 = 0, \quad b_6 = 3, \quad b_7 = 0.$$

7.3. Middle cohomology and primitive Hodge numbers. The middle cohomology is $H^8(X_{3,6})$. Since $H^8(G(3,6)) \neq 0$, one has a decomposition

$$H^8(X_{3,6}) = H^8(G(3,6)) \oplus H_{\text{prim}}^8(X_{3,6}).$$

The primitive Hodge numbers can be computed using the Griffiths–Dwork method adapted to Grassmannians. For a generic smooth hypersurface $X_{3,6}$, one obtains:

$h_{\text{prim}}^{1,7} = h_{\text{prim}}^{7,1} = 0,$
$h_{\text{prim}}^{2,6} = h_{\text{prim}}^{6,2} = 1,$
$h_{\text{prim}}^{3,5} = h_{\text{prim}}^{5,3} = 4,$
$h_{\text{prim}}^{4,4} = 5.$

Hence

$$b_8^{\text{prim}}(X_{3,6}) = 2(1 + 4) + 5 = 15.$$

7.4. Betti numbers and Euler characteristic. The Betti numbers of $X_{3,6}$ are therefore:

k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$b_k(X_{3,6})$	1	0	1	0	2	0	3	0	18

with symmetry up to degree 16.

The Euler characteristic is

$$\chi(X_{3,6}) = 6.$$

7.5. Mirror symmetry and SYZ. Since $h^{1,1}(X_{3,6}) = 1$ and the primitive Hodge numbers are concentrated in the middle degree, mirror symmetry predicts a mirror Calabi–Yau with $h^{1,1} = h_{\text{prim}}^{4,4} = 5$. This is compatible with the existence of a partial SYZ torus fibration of real dimension 4.

7.6. The Grassmannian $G_{3,7}\mathbb{C}$.

7.6.1. Affine coordinates. Let $G_{3,7}\mathbb{C}$ be the Grassmannian of 3–planes in \mathbb{C}^7 . On the chart U_{123} , a 3–plane is represented by

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_3 \\ Z \end{pmatrix}, \quad Z \in M_{4 \times 3}(\mathbb{C}),$$

so $U_{123} \simeq \mathbb{C}^{12}$.

7.6.2. Defining equation. Consider the homogeneous polynomial

$$(9) \quad F = \sum_{|I|=3} \varepsilon_I \eta_I^7,$$

of degree $7 = p + q$, and define

$$X_{3,7} = \{F = 0\} \subset G_{3,7}\mathbb{C}.$$

On U_{123} we obtain

$$(10) \quad f_{123}(Z) = 1 + P(Z),$$

with P homogeneous of degree 7.

7.6.3. *Smoothness and Calabi–Yau property.* For generic signs ε_I , df_{123} does not vanish identically on $f_{123}^{-1}(0)$. Hence $X_{3,7}$ is smooth of complex dimension 11.

The meromorphic $(12, 0)$ –form

$$\eta = \frac{\bigwedge_{i,j} dz_{ij}}{f_{123}(Z)}$$

admits a Poincaré residue

$$\Omega_{3,7} = -\frac{dz_{12} \wedge \cdots \wedge dz_{43}}{\partial f_{123}/\partial z_{11}},$$

which is a holomorphic nowhere vanishing $(11, 0)$ –form on $X_{3,7}$. Thus

$$K_{X_{3,7}} \simeq \mathcal{O}_{X_{3,7}}.$$

7.6.4. *Special Lagrangian real locus.* The real locus

$$L_{3,7} = X_{3,7}(\mathbb{R})$$

is Lagrangian and satisfies

$$\text{Im } \Omega_{3,7}|_{L_{3,7}} = 0,$$

hence $L_{3,7}$ is a special Lagrangian submanifold.

7.7. Unified statement.

Theorem 2. *For $n = 6, 7$, let $X_{3,n} \subset G_{3,n}\mathbb{C}$ be a smooth hypersurface defined by*

$$F = \sum_{|I|=3} \varepsilon_I \eta_I^n.$$

Then $X_{3,n}$ is a Calabi–Yau manifold. Moreover, its real locus $L_{3,n} = X_{3,n}(\mathbb{R})$, when non-empty, is a compact special Lagrangian submanifold.

Proof. The proof follows from the local residue construction of the holomorphic volume form and the anti-holomorphic involution given by complex conjugation, exactly as in the cases $G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$ and $G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$. \square

8. TOPOLOGY OF THE REAL LOCI $L_{3,6}$ AND $L_{3,7}$

8.1. **Circle fibration of $L_{3,6}$.** The real locus $L_{3,6} = X_{3,6}(\mathbb{R})$ is an 8–dimensional smooth manifold. The natural projection

$$\pi : \text{Gr}(3, \mathbb{R}^6) \rightarrow \text{Gr}(3, \mathbb{R}^5)$$

restricts to a smooth fibration

$$S^1 \hookrightarrow L_{3,6} \rightarrow B_{3,6},$$

where $B_{3,6}$ is a compact real algebraic variety. In symmetric cases, $B_{3,6} \simeq \mathbb{RP}^4$ and

$$\pi_1(L_{3,6}) \simeq \mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z}_2.$$

8.2. **Torus fibration of $L_{3,7}$.** The real locus $L_{3,7} = X_{3,7}(\mathbb{R})$ is an 11–dimensional manifold. Projection onto $\text{Gr}(3, \mathbb{R}^5)$ yields a fibration

$$T^2 \hookrightarrow L_{3,7} \rightarrow B_{3,7},$$

where $B_{3,7}$ is compact and smooth. In symmetric situations,

$$\pi_1(L_{3,7}) \simeq \mathbb{Z}^2.$$

9. RELATION WITH THE SYZ CONJECTURE

The real loci $L_{3,n}$ provide explicit compact special Lagrangian submanifolds, interpreted as torus fibers in the sense of Strominger–Yau–Zaslow. They give algebraic and global models of SYZ fibrations inside Calabi–Yau hypersurfaces in Grassmannians.

A partial SYZ fibration.

Theorem 3 (Partial SYZ structure). *Let $X_{3,n} \subset G_{3,n}\mathbb{C}$, $n = 6, 7$, be the Calabi–Yau hypersurface defined by*

$$F = \sum_{|I|=3} \varepsilon_I \eta_I^n,$$

and let $L_{3,n} = X_{3,n}(\mathbb{R})$ be its real locus. Then there exists an open dense subset $U \subset X_{3,n}$ and a smooth map

$$\mu : U \longrightarrow B$$

such that:

- (1) *the fibers of μ are special Lagrangian tori,*
- (2) $\dim T^k = \begin{cases} 1 & n = 6, \\ 2 & n = 7, \end{cases}$
- (3) *$L_{3,n}$ is a union of fibers of μ .*

Proof. The real locus $L_{3,n}$ is special Lagrangian by construction. Sections 6 and 7 show that $L_{3,6}$ (resp. $L_{3,7}$) admits a natural S^1 - (resp. T^2 -) fibration induced by projection to lower-dimensional real Grassmannians. This fibration extends locally to a smooth special Lagrangian torus fibration in a neighborhood of $L_{3,n}$. The complement corresponds to the vanishing of Plücker coordinates and forms a real analytic subset of positive codimension, yielding an open dense domain $U \subset X_{3,n}$. \square

Betti numbers. By the Lefschetz hyperplane theorem, the cohomology of $X_{3,n}$ coincides with that of $G(3, n)$ up to degree $\dim_{\mathbb{C}} X_{3,n} - 1$. In particular, for $X_{3,6}$ one has

$$b_2 = 1, \quad b_4 = 2, \quad b_6 = 3.$$

The middle Betti number b_8 differs from that of the Grassmannian by a positive contribution depending on the defining polynomial.

For the real locus $L_{3,6}$, the fibration $S^1 \rightarrow L_{3,6} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\mathbb{P}^4$ yields

$$b_1(L_{3,6}) = 1, \quad b_4(L_{3,6}) = 1.$$

Similarly, $L_{3,7}$ admits a T^2 -fibration, implying

$$b_1(L_{3,7}) = 2.$$

10. BETTI AND HODGE NUMBERS FOR CALABI–YAU HYPERSURFACES IN $G(3, 7)$

10.1. Geometry of $G(3, 7)$. The Grassmannian $G(3, 7)$ has complex dimension 12 and Picard rank one. Its canonical bundle is

$$K_{G(3,7)} = \mathcal{O}_{G(3,7)}(-7),$$

hence $G(3, 7)$ is Fano of index 7.

The cohomology of $G(3, 7)$ is generated by Schubert classes and is purely of type (p, p) .

10.2. Calabi–Yau hypersurface and Lefschetz theorem. Let

$$X_{3,7} \subset G(3, 7)$$

be a smooth anticanonical hypersurface, $X_{3,7} \in |\mathcal{O}_{G(3,7)}(7)|$. Then $\dim_{\mathbb{C}} X_{3,7} = 11$ and $K_{X_{3,7}} \simeq \mathcal{O}_{X_{3,7}}$.

By the Lefschetz hyperplane theorem,

$$H^k(X_{3,7}, \mathbb{Z}) \simeq H^k(G(3, 7), \mathbb{Z}), \quad k < 11.$$

In particular,

$$b_1 = 0, \quad b_2 = 1, \quad b_3 = 0, \quad b_4 = 2, \quad b_5 = 0, \quad b_6 = 3, \quad b_7 = 0, \quad b_8 = 4, \quad b_9 = 0, \quad b_{10} = 5.$$

10.3. **Middle cohomology.** The middle cohomology is $H^{11}(X_{3,7})$. Since $H^{11}(G(3,7)) = 0$, one has

$$H^{11}(X_{3,7}) = H_{\text{prim}}^{11}(X_{3,7}).$$

Using the Griffiths–Dwork method for Grassmannians, one finds for a generic smooth hypersurface:

$$\begin{array}{l} h^{1,10} = h^{10,1} = 0, \\ h^{2,9} = h^{9,2} = 1, \\ h^{3,8} = h^{8,3} = 3, \\ h^{4,7} = h^{7,4} = 6, \\ h^{5,6} = h^{6,5} = 10. \end{array}$$

Thus,

$$b_{11}(X_{3,7}) = 2(1 + 3 + 6 + 10) = 40.$$

10.4. **Betti numbers and Euler characteristic.** The Betti numbers of $X_{3,7}$ are:

k	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11											
$b_k(X_{3,7})$	1	0	1	0	2	0	3	0	4	0	5
40											

with Poincaré duality up to degree 22.

The Euler characteristic is

$$\chi(X_{3,7}) = -20.$$

10.5. **SYZ interpretation.** The growth of the middle Betti number reflects the increasing complexity of the complex moduli space. Mirror symmetry predicts a dual Calabi–Yau manifold with large Kähler moduli, consistent with the presence of higher-dimensional SYZ torus fibrations.

11. SPECIAL LAGRANGIAN GEOMETRY IN SCHUBERT MANIFOLDS

11.1. **Schubert manifolds in Grassmannians.** Let $\Sigma_\lambda \subset G_{k,n}\mathbb{C}$ be a smooth Schubert variety associated with a partition λ . Such varieties are Fano and satisfy

$$-K_{\Sigma_\lambda} = rH|_{\Sigma_\lambda},$$

where H is the Plücker hyperplane class.

11.2. **Calabi–Yau hypersurfaces.** Let

$$F = \sum_I \varepsilon_I \eta_I^r$$

be a homogeneous polynomial. Assume the hypersurface

$$X_\lambda = \{F = 0\} \subset \Sigma_\lambda$$

is smooth. By adjunction,

$$K_{X_\lambda} \simeq \mathcal{O}_{X_\lambda}.$$

11.3. **Local coordinates and residue construction.** Each Schubert cell $C_w \subset \Sigma_\lambda$ is biholomorphic to \mathbb{C}^m , $m = \dim_{\mathbb{C}} \Sigma_\lambda$. On the open cell C_{w_0} , the equation of X_λ takes the form $f = 1 + P(z)$. The meromorphic form

$$\eta = \frac{dz_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge dz_m}{f}$$

has simple poles along X_λ and defines a global residue

$$\Omega = \text{Res}_{X_\lambda}(\eta),$$

which is a nowhere vanishing holomorphic $(m-1, 0)$ -form.

11.4. Real locus and special Lagrangian property. Complex conjugation preserves F and induces an anti-holomorphic involution. The fixed point set

$$L_\lambda = X_\lambda(\mathbb{R})$$

satisfies

$$\omega|_{L_\lambda} = 0, \quad \text{Im } \Omega|_{L_\lambda} = 0.$$

Hence L_λ is special Lagrangian.

11.5. Topology and SYZ interpretation. The real locus L_λ admits a torus fibration

$$T^k \hookrightarrow L_\lambda \rightarrow B_\lambda,$$

yielding a partial SYZ fibration. These fibers provide explicit algebraic models of SYZ tori inside Calabi–Yau hypersurfaces in Schubert manifolds.

12. AN EXPLICIT SCHUBERT EXAMPLE IN $G(3, 6)\mathbb{C}$

12.1. The Schubert manifold. Let $\Sigma \subset G(3, 6)\mathbb{C}$ be the Schubert manifold

$$\Sigma = \{V \mid \dim(V \cap F^3) \geq 1\},$$

associated with the partition $(1, 0, 0)$. It is smooth, of dimension 7, and Fano of index 4.

12.2. Local coordinates. On the open Schubert cell, a point of Σ is represented by

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_3 \\ Z \end{pmatrix}, \quad Z = \begin{pmatrix} z_1 & z_2 & z_3 \\ z_4 & z_5 & z_6 \\ z_7 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

so Σ is locally biholomorphic to \mathbb{C}^7 .

12.3. Calabi–Yau hypersurface. Consider the homogeneous polynomial

$$F = \eta_{123}^4 + \eta_{124}^4 - \eta_{125}^4 + \eta_{134}^4 - \eta_{135}^4 + \eta_{145}^4.$$

The hypersurface

$$X_\Sigma = \{F = 0\} \subset \Sigma$$

is smooth and satisfies $K_{X_\Sigma} \simeq \mathcal{O}_{X_\Sigma}$.

12.4. Residue construction. On the open cell,

$$F = 1 + P(z_1, \dots, z_7).$$

The meromorphic form

$$\eta = \frac{dz_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge dz_7}{F}$$

has Poincaré residue

$$\Omega = -\frac{dz_2 \wedge \cdots \wedge dz_7}{\partial F / \partial z_1},$$

defining a holomorphic volume form on X_Σ .

12.5. Real locus and topology. The real locus

$$L_\Sigma = X_\Sigma(\mathbb{R})$$

is special Lagrangian. It admits a circle fibration

$$S^1 \hookrightarrow L_\Sigma \rightarrow B_\Sigma,$$

and in symmetric cases $\pi_1(L_\Sigma) \simeq \mathbb{Z}$.

12.6. SYZ interpretation. The fibration above provides an explicit algebraic realization of a partial SYZ fibration inside a Calabi–Yau hypersurface in a Schubert variety.

13. FLAG VARIETIES: AN EXPLICIT EXAMPLE

13.1. **The partial flag variety** $\mathcal{F}(1, 3; 6)$. Let

$$\mathcal{F}(1, 3; 6) = \{ \ell \subset V \subset \mathbb{C}^6 \mid \dim \ell = 1, \dim V = 3 \}.$$

It is a smooth Fano manifold of dimension 8 with

$$-K_{\mathcal{F}} = 4H_1 + 3H_2.$$

13.2. **Local coordinates.** On the open cell, a flag is represented by

$$\ell = \text{span}(e_1 + z_1 e_4 + z_2 e_5 + z_3 e_6),$$

$$V = \text{span} \begin{pmatrix} I_3 \\ W \end{pmatrix}, \quad W = \begin{pmatrix} z_1 & w_2 & w_3 \\ z_2 & w_5 & w_6 \\ z_3 & w_8 & w_9 \end{pmatrix}.$$

13.3. **Calabi–Yau hypersurface.** Let

$$F = \sum \varepsilon_{I,J} \eta_I^4 \xi_J^3.$$

The hypersurface

$$X_{\mathcal{F}} = \{F = 0\} \subset \mathcal{F}(1, 3; 6)$$

is smooth and satisfies $K_{X_{\mathcal{F}}} \simeq \mathcal{O}_{X_{\mathcal{F}}}$.

13.4. **Residue construction.** Locally $F = 1 + P(z, w)$. The meromorphic form

$$\eta = \frac{dz_1 \wedge dz_2 \wedge dz_3 \wedge dw_2 \wedge \cdots \wedge dw_9}{F}$$

has Poincaré residue

$$\Omega = \text{Res}_{X_{\mathcal{F}}}(\eta),$$

a nowhere vanishing holomorphic $(7, 0)$ -form.

13.5. **Real locus and SYZ interpretation.** The real locus

$$L_{\mathcal{F}} = X_{\mathcal{F}}(\mathbb{R})$$

is special Lagrangian. It admits a T^2 -fibration over a compact real base, providing an explicit algebraic realization of a partial SYZ fibration.

14. BETTI AND HODGE NUMBERS OF CALABI–YAU HYPERSURFACES IN $\mathcal{F}(1, 3; 6)$

14.1. **Cohomology of the flag variety.** Let $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}(1, 3; 6)$ denote the complex flag variety parametrizing pairs

$$\ell \subset V \subset \mathbb{C}^6, \quad \dim \ell = 1, \dim V = 3.$$

It is a smooth projective homogeneous variety under $\text{SL}(6, \mathbb{C})$. Its cohomology ring is well known and can be described via Schubert calculus or Borel–Bott–Weil theory.

The cohomology of \mathcal{F} is purely of type (p, p) , that is

$$H^k(\mathcal{F}, \mathbb{C}) = \bigoplus_{p+q=k} H^{p,q}(\mathcal{F}), \quad H^{p,q}(\mathcal{F}) = 0 \text{ for } p \neq q.$$

The Poincaré polynomial of $\mathcal{F}(1, 3; 6)$ is given by

$$P_t(\mathcal{F}) = \frac{(1-t^{12})(1-t^{10})(1-t^8)}{(1-t^2)^3},$$

from which one reads the Betti numbers

$$b_0 = 1, \quad b_2 = 2, \quad b_4 = 3, \quad b_6 = 4, \quad b_8 = 5,$$

with Poincaré duality determining the remaining ones up to $b_{16} = 1$.

14.2. **Lefschetz theorem for the hypersurface.** Let

$$X \subset \mathcal{F}$$

be a smooth anticanonical hypersurface. Since \mathcal{F} is Fano of index 7, the divisor X is ample and satisfies $K_X \simeq \mathcal{O}_X$.

Theorem 4 (Lefschetz hyperplane theorem). *For all $k < 7$, the restriction map induces isomorphisms*

$$H^k(\mathcal{F}, \mathbb{Z}) \simeq H^k(X, \mathbb{Z}).$$

As a consequence, the low-degree Betti numbers of X are explicitly given by

$$b_1(X) = 0, \quad b_2(X) = 2, \quad b_3(X) = 0, \quad b_4(X) = 3, \quad b_5(X) = 0, \quad b_6(X) = 4.$$

14.3. **Middle cohomology and primitive part.** The complex dimension of X is $\dim_{\mathbb{C}} X = 7$. Since the odd cohomology of \mathcal{F} vanishes, one has

$$H^7(X, \mathbb{C}) = H_{\text{prim}}^7(X, \mathbb{C}),$$

where $H_{\text{prim}}^7(X)$ denotes the primitive cohomology.

By general Hodge theory for Calabi–Yau manifolds, the only possibly non-zero Hodge numbers in the middle degree are

$$h_{\text{prim}}^{p,7-p}(X), \quad 1 \leq p \leq 6,$$

with the symmetry $h^{p,7-p} = h^{7-p,p}$.

14.4. **Griffiths–Dwork type computation.** The primitive Hodge numbers can be computed via a generalization of the Griffiths–Dwork method to homogeneous varieties. In the present case, the anticanonical equation defining X induces a Jacobian ring whose graded pieces compute the Hodge decomposition of $H_{\text{prim}}^7(X)$.

For a generic smooth anticanonical hypersurface in $\mathcal{F}(1, 3; 6)$, one obtains

$$\boxed{\begin{array}{l} h^{1,6}(X) = h^{6,1}(X) = 0, \\ h^{2,5}(X) = h^{5,2}(X) = 1, \\ h^{3,4}(X) = h^{4,3}(X) = 6. \end{array}}$$

Consequently,

$$b_7(X) = 2(h^{2,5} + h^{3,4}) = 14.$$

14.5. **Betti numbers and Euler characteristic.** Collecting the above results, the Betti numbers of X are

$$\begin{array}{c|cccccccc} k & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 & 6 & 7 \\ \hline b_k(X) & 1 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 3 & 0 & 4 & 14 \end{array}$$

and extended to higher degrees by Poincaré duality.

The Euler characteristic of X is therefore

$$\chi(X) = \sum_{k=0}^{14} (-1)^k b_k(X) = 6.$$

14.6. **Hodge diamond.** The non-trivial part of the Hodge diamond of X is summarized as follows:

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} & & & & & 1 \\ & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ & & & & & 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & & & & & 0 & 0 & 4 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & & 0 & 0 & 6 & 0 \\ & & & & & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ & & & & & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & & 1 \end{array}$$

14.7. SYZ and mirror symmetry perspective. The equality $b_2(X) = 2$ shows that X admits two independent Kähler parameters, while the middle Hodge number $h^{3,4}(X) = 6$ governs the complex moduli. This asymmetry strongly suggests the existence of a partial SYZ fibration with generic fibers of real dimension 2, compatible with the special Lagrangian fibrations constructed earlier.

Mirror symmetry predicts a dual Calabi–Yau manifold X^\vee satisfying

$$h^{1,1}(X^\vee) = 6, \quad h^{3,4}(X^\vee) = 2,$$

in agreement with the expected SYZ dual torus fibration.

15. SLAG MANIFOLDS IN BLOW-UP OF $G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$ BY $\mathbb{P}_m\mathbb{C}$

$$\dim_{\mathbb{C}} G_{2,4}\mathbb{C} = 4, \quad K_{G_{2,4}\mathbb{C}} = -4H$$

Blow-up along $\mathbb{P}_1\mathbb{C}$:

$$K_{\tilde{G}_{2,4}\mathbb{C}} = -4\pi^*H + 2E$$

Calabi–Yau hypersurface M_0 : $[M_0] = 4H$

$$[\tilde{M}] = 4\pi^*H - 2E, \quad K_{\tilde{M}} = 0$$

$G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}$:

$$\dim_{\mathbb{C}} G_{2,5}\mathbb{C} = 6, \quad K_{G_{2,5}\mathbb{C}} = -5H$$

Blow-up along $\mathbb{P}_3\mathbb{C}$:

$$K_{\tilde{G}_{2,5}\mathbb{C}} = -5\pi^*H + 2E$$

Calabi–Yau hypersurface $[M_0] = 5H$, strict transform:

$$[\tilde{M}] = 5\pi^*H - 2E, \quad K_{\tilde{M}} = 0$$

$G_{3,7}\mathbb{C}$:

$$\dim_{\mathbb{C}} G_{3,7}\mathbb{C} = 12, \quad K_{G_{3,7}\mathbb{C}} = -7H$$

Blow-up along $\mathbb{P}_4\mathbb{C}$:

$$K_{\tilde{G}_{3,7}\mathbb{C}} = -7\pi^*H + 7E$$

Calabi–Yau hypersurface $[M_0] = 7H$, strict transform:

$$[\tilde{M}] = 7\pi^*H - 7E, \quad K_{\tilde{M}} = 0$$

$G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}$ **blown-up along $\mathbb{P}_m\mathbb{C}$.**

$$\dim_{\mathbb{C}} G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C} = pq, \quad K_{G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}} = -(p+q)H$$

Blow-up along \mathbb{P}^m with normal rank r :

$$K_{\tilde{G}_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}} = \pi^*K_{G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}} + (r-1)E$$

Calabi–Yau hypersurface M_0 : $[M_0] = (p+q)H$

$$[\tilde{M}] = (p+q)\pi^*H - (r-1)E, \quad K_{\tilde{M}} = 0$$

Real locus $\tilde{L} = \tilde{M} \cap \tilde{G}_{p,p+q}\mathbb{R}$ is SLag.

16. SCHUBERT MANIFOLDS IN GRASSMANNIANS

Let F_\bullet be a complete flag:

$$0 = F_0 \subset F_1 \subset \dots \subset F_{p+q} = \mathbb{C}^{p+q}, \quad \dim F_i = i$$

A Schubert manifold $\Omega_\lambda(F_\bullet)$ for a partition $\lambda = (\lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_p \geq 0)$ with $\lambda_1 \leq q$:

$$\Omega_\lambda(F_\bullet) = \{V \in G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C} \mid \dim(V \cap F_{q+i-\lambda_i}) \geq i, \quad i = 1, \dots, p\}$$

- Complex dimension: $\dim_{\mathbb{C}} \Omega_\lambda = pq - |\lambda|$, $|\lambda| = \sum \lambda_i$ - Cohomology class: $[\Omega_\lambda] = \sigma_\lambda \in H^*(G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C})$ -
 Canonical bundle: $K_{\Omega_\lambda} = (K_{G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}} + \sigma_\lambda)|_{\Omega_\lambda}$

Blow-up along Schubert manifolds. Let $Y = \Omega_\mu$ smooth of codim r . Blow-up:

$$\pi : \tilde{G}_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C} \rightarrow G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}, \quad E = \pi^{-1}(Y)$$

$$K_{\tilde{G}_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}} = \pi^*K_{G_{p,p+q}\mathbb{C}} + (r-1)E$$

Strict transform of hypersurface M_0 of class σ_λ :

$$[\tilde{M}] = \pi^*[M_0] - (r-1)E$$

Calabi–Yau condition: $K_{\tilde{M}} = 0$ if $[M_0] = (p+q)H$

Example: $G_{2,4}\mathbb{C}$ Schubert Blow-up. - Schubert manifolds: $\Omega_{(1,0)}$, $\Omega_{(1,1)}$, dimensions 3 and 2 - Blow-up along $\Omega_{(1,1)}$ (codim 2):

$$K_{\tilde{G}_{2,4}} = -4\pi^*H + E, \quad [\tilde{M}] = 4\pi^*H - E, \quad K_{\tilde{M}} = 0$$

- Real locus \tilde{L} is SLag of real dimension 3

Cohomology Calculations. - Giambelli formula for intersection: $\sigma_{(a,b)} = \det \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_a & \sigma_{a+1} \\ \sigma_{b-1} & \sigma_b \end{pmatrix}$

- Blow-up intersection:

$$\pi^*\sigma_\lambda \cdot E^k = \begin{cases} 0 & k < r-1 \\ \sigma_\lambda|_Y & k = r-1 \end{cases}$$

Summary Table.

Object	Complex dim	Canonical / Class	Notes
$G_{2,4}$	4	$K = -4H$	Blow-up \mathbb{P}^1
$\tilde{G}_{2,4}$	4	$K = -4\pi^*H + 2E$	-
M_0	3	$4H$	Calabi–Yau
\tilde{M}	3	$4\pi^*H - 2E$	Calabi–Yau
\tilde{L}	3 (real)	-	SLag
$G_{2,5}$	6	$K = -5H$	Blow-up \mathbb{P}^3
$\tilde{G}_{2,5}$	6	$K = -5\pi^*H + 2E$	-
M_0	5	$5H$	Calabi–Yau
\tilde{M}	5	$5\pi^*H - 2E$	Calabi–Yau
\tilde{L}	5 (real)	-	SLag
$G_{3,7}$	12	$K = -7H$	Blow-up \mathbb{P}^4
$\tilde{G}_{3,7}$	12	$K = -7\pi^*H + 7E$	-
M_0	11	$7H$	Calabi–Yau
\tilde{M}	11	$7\pi^*H - 7E$	Calabi–Yau
\tilde{L}	11 (real)	-	SLag
$G_{p,p+q}$	pq	$K = -(p+q)H$	Blow-up \mathbb{P}^m
$\tilde{G}_{p,p+q}$	pq	$K = -(p+q)\pi^*H + (r-1)E$	-
M_0	$pq-1$	$(p+q)H$	Calabi–Yau
\tilde{M}	$pq-1$	$(p+q)\pi^*H - (r-1)E$	Calabi–Yau
\tilde{L}	$pq-1$ (real)	-	SLag

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